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ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Home

Home. How beautiful the word home sounds
In my eyes, it seems like paradise when found
In this world full of turmoil and unrest
In life's once-chaotic flow, it serves as a calm and a rest.

Memory. A bitter spark that has left me in pain
The memory of yesterday that cannot be buried in the brain
The one who truly loves is the one left behind
The one willing to fight is always defeated, always resigned.

Solitude. Gazing at the stars as if they know my sorrow
How in solitude there is no peace, only pain to follow
Even the birds' songs seem like melodies of defeat and gloom
In the test of love, when is the right time to let go of its bloom?

Illusion. Life's music seems to have become so complex
Your promises, sweet as sugar, I thought were correct
I thought it was only me, I thought there was no other, I thought we would stay till the end
A mistake it was, to give you all the trust I could send.

Hope. Deceived by lies, here I am seeking peace in the waves
That with every crash might ease the sorrow that love gave
May the drops of tears forced upon my eyes be erased
As I dive deep, may I wake forgetting your memories' trace. Hope.

Chapter. I do not know if the page of sorrow has already closed
Yet on the other side is a whisper to rise and let life be composed
In this new chapter, waiting is no longer a burden to bear
For the sake of a love that is certain and fair.

Destiny. Sometimes lonely, not forced, and sometimes beyond control
Those were the words I uttered when I first saw your soul
My heart grew calm, each beat light and free
Filled with an unexplainable joy – you are my destiny.

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Shelter. By your side, the pain of the past is unknown
So, this is how it feels to be loved, to be chosen, and shown
Not forced. You are my shelter, my rest, my peace
Not perfect, but whole and sure, a love that will not cease.

Home. How beautiful the word home sounds
And even more beautiful when a home is truly found
You are the light in my twilight, in you I am safe and free
You are my home, my beloved, my serenity.